

PAXTADAN CHIQUADIGAN CHIQUINDILARI TARKIBIDAGI YIGIRISH UCHUN YAROQLI TOLALARNI AJRATISH QURILMASINI SXEMASINI YARATISH VA UNI SAMARALI ISHLASHINI ASOSLASH

Toxirov A'zamjon Ibrohim o'g'li

Andijon mashinasozlik instituti

Tayanch doktoranti

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Annotatsiya: Ma'lumki, maqolada paxta chiqindilarini tarkibidagi yigiruvga yaroqli tolalar qushilib ketishini bilamiz, shu bois taklif etilayotgan qurilmada paxta chiqindilari yigiruvga yaroqli tolalari ajratish keltirilgan. Qurilma ignali baraban va pichoqlar yordamida ajratilgan asosan boshqa qurilmalardan farqi bitti baraban bilan amalga oshirilgan. Maqolada pichoqlar va ignali baraban bilan orasidagi masofalar keltirilgan hamda optimali olingan va har bir o'tkazilgan tajribalarni jadvallar yordamida keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Tola, chiqindi, shytoka, baraban, igna, ulyuk, cho'tkali baraban, pichoq, arrali lenta, patrubka, shnek.

It is known that in the article we know that the composition of cotton waste is connected to fibers suitable for spinning, so the proposed device offers the separation of fibers suitable for spinning in cotton waste. The device is separated by needle drums and blades, basically the difference from other devices is that one is fastened with a drum. The article lists the distances between the blades and the needle drum and presents the optimal obtained and conducted experiments with each using tables.

Keywords: fiber, waste, slate, barbell, Needle, Thread, brush drum, knife, saw tape, cartridge, cord.

KIRISH

To'qimachilik korxonasi qimmatbaho xomashyosi bo'lgan paxta tolasining o'rtacha 3-4 foizi tolali chiqindilar tarkibiga qo'shilib ketadi. Bu avvalo qimmatbaho tolaning yo'qolishiga, ikkinchi tomondan sifatining buzilishiga olib keladi. Taklif qilinayotgan qurilmani joriy qilish orqali chiqayotgan momikli

aralashma tarkibidagi yigirishga yaroqli uzun tolalarni ajratib olish imkoniyati yaratiladi.

Ulyuk

Ulyuk tarkibidan ajratib olingan tola

Qo'yilgan vazifani xal qilish maqsadida chiqindi tarkibidagi yigiruvga yaroqli tolalarni ajratish qurilmasini yaratishni maqsad qilib olindi. Buning natijasida korxonada tola chiqish miqdori oshadi va yaxshilanadi. Qurilmani taklif qilishdan maqsad chiqindi tarkibiga qo'shib ketayotgan uzun tolalarni ajratib olib, korxonada tola chiqishi miqdorining oshirish va uzun tolalarni chiqindi tarkibiga qo'shib ketishini oldini olish orqali chiqindi tarkibidan tola ajratib olishdan iborat.

Taklif qilinayotgan qurilma quyidagi asosiy elementlardan iborat: paxta chiqindisi; riflyonli valik; baraban; cho'tka; arrali lenta pichoq; cho'tkali baraban; tola; patrubka (1-rasm).

Ushbu qurilma quyidagicha ishlaydi: kirish quvuri 1 orqali chiqindi kiradi va 2 shyotka orqali ignali baraban 3 ga keladi va baraban ignalari yordamida uzun tolalalar ilib olinadi xamda aylanishi tufayli pichoqlarga 4 ga uriladi, cho'tkali barabanga keladi va cho'tkali baraban 5 yordamida ignalardan sidirib olinib, tola chiqish quvuri 6 orqali chiqariladi.

Masalani yechilishi: Mazkur qurilmaning tajriba nusxasi tayyorlangan bo'lib, unda dastlabki sinovlar o'tkazib ko'rildi va sinovlar natijasiga ko'ra haqiqatdan ham 1-2 % uzun tolalar chiqindi tarkibiga qo'shib ketib, qimmatbaho xomashyoning yo'qolishiga sabab bo'lishi aniqlandi.

Tolaning uzunligini tavsiflovchi xossalari ichida uzunlik bo'yicha bir tekisda taqsimlanishi muhim texnologik ahamiyatga ega. SHu sababli tajribalar bir necha marotaba takrorlandi.

1- rasm. Paxta chiqindilari tarkibidagi yigiruvga yaroqli tolalarni ajratib oluvchi qurilmani Birinchi tadqiqot bo'yicha olingan natijalar o'rtachasi 1- jadvalda keltirilgan.

1- jadval

№	CHiqindilar olingan kalava ip yigiruv korxonasi	CHiqindilar namunalari, 100 grammdan	Paxta chiqindisi, Standart-3,7,11	
			Toza tola gramm	Iflos aralashma gramm
1	Nam teks. (Namangan)	100	79.46	20.54
2	RUSO-UZBEK-TEKS (Farg'ona)	100	70.69	29.31
3	AL-YOR-TEKS. (Andijon)	100	76.05	23.95

2 - rasm. Paxta chiqindilari tarkibidagi yigiruvga yaroqli tolalarni ajratib oluvchi qurilmani.

2- jadval

№2-tadqiqot bo'yicha olingan natijalari o'rtachasi

№	Chiqindilar olingan kalava ip yigiruv korxonasi	CHiqindilar namunalari, 100 grammdan	Paxta chiqindisi, Standart-3,7,11	
			Toza tola gramm	Iflos aralashma gramm
1	Nam teks. (Namangan)	100	77.19	22.81
2	RUSO-UZBEK-TEKS (Farg'ona)	100	71.95	28.05
3	AL-YOR-TEKS. (Andijon)	100	67.85	32.15

3 – rasm. Paxta chiqindilari tarkibidagi yigiruvga yaroqli tolalarni ajratib oluvchi qurilma garniturası

3- jadval

№3-tadqiqot bo'yicha olingan natijalari o'rtachasi

№	Chiqindilar olingan kalava ip yigiruv korxonasi	CHiqindilar namunalari, 100 grammdan	Paxta chiqindisi, Standart-3,7,11	
			Toza tola gramm	Iflos aralashma gramm
1	Nam teks. (Namangan)	100	79.04	20.96
2	RUSO-UZBEK-TEKS (Farg'ona)	100	74.08	25.92
3	AL-YOR-TEKS. (Andijon)	100	72.93	27.07

Paxta chiqindilari tarkibidagi yigiruvga yaroqli tolalarni ajratib oluvchi qurilmani №1-2-3- tadqiqot bo'yicha olingan natijalari o'rtachasi

№	CHiqindilar olingan kalava ip yigiruv korxonasi	CHiqindilar namunalari, 100 grammdan	Paxta chiqindisi, Standart-3,7,11	
			Toza tola gramm	Iflos aralashma gramm
1	Nam teks. (Namangan), RUSO-UZBEK-TEKS (Farg'ona), AL-YOR-TEKS.(Andijon) korxolarni O'rtachasi	100	74.35	25.65

Yuqoridagi jadval bo'yicha xulosa qilinsa, kalava ip yigirish korxonalarining paxta chiqindilari (tarandilari)ning o'rtacha hisobda 74.35 foizini toza tola va 25.65 foizini esa yaroqsiz iflos aralashmalar tashkil qilmoqda. Bundan ko'rinib turibdiki tadqiqotlar natijasida qurilmaga eng maqbul TSMPLi baraban bilan pichoqlar orasidagi masofani birinchi tadqiqot bo'yicha olingan, undan kam qilinsa pichoqlarni sonini toza tolalar miqdori iflos aralashma chiqindilariga ko'p chiqib ketadi.

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